

A CORPUS BASED DIACHRONIC STUDY OF VERB COMPLEMENTATION PATTERN IN PAKISTANI ENGLISH

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Original Article

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Abstract

This study is about the verb complementation pattern of Pakistani English. Corpus based approach was adopted to conduct the diachronic study. Corpus from 1947 to 1986 was collected and divided into the four decades. Main concern of the study was to conduct the comparative study about the use of (to infinitive) and gerund as verb complement and to see the change with the passage of time about these complementation patterns. Twenty verbs were selected with the help of grammars and the research conducted by (Aziz 2010) and reported the verbs which carry (to infinitive) pattern. Those twenty common verbs were selected with on the basis of research and with the help of grammar which carry both these patterns. Corpus was analyzed with the help of Antconc concordance lines were developed of these verbs and each verb with its concordance and all forms of verbs were studied separately. Results of the study showed Pakistani writers use (to infinitive) pattern at a higher frequency than gerund as verb complementation and this tendency changed with the passage of time. Results of the 1st corpus higher frequency of gerund but with the passage of time this tendency changed and frequency of (to infinitive) increased. It can be concluded from the study that use of gerund which works as noun makes the process of nominalization. Nominalization makes the writing more complex, Pakistani being non-native avoid the use of gerund and use (to infinitive) at a higher frequency and keep the writing simple.

Keywords: Corpus, diachronic, verb complement, gerund, to infinitive, Pakistani English

1.0 Introduction

Language variation has been a key interest of all the linguists. Philologists were mainly concerned to find out the relation and similarities of 'Proto languages' in a language family. Dialectology was there to study the variations created to by the influence of difference in region. In the latter half of 20th century 'Sociolinguistics' emerged as an independent discipline.

Sociolinguistics is mainly concerned to study language variation caused on the basis of region, class, race, ethnicity and so on. Sociolinguistics focuses on the relation between languages society, the impact which society has on language usage. Sociolinguistics leads to the area of 'World Englishes'.

English as the language of Britain combination of Anglo-Saxons and Anglo-Norman in the 7th century. English was initially the language of British areas only and later spread in the whole world. Jenkins (2003) divided the process of spread in in two 'diasporas'. English language practiced in the native and non-native countries is 'institutionalized English' these varieties have different phonological, lexical and grammatical differences (kachru, 1988; talaat 1993). Differences in the use of words are observed and different grammatical patterns are found in all varieties.

The rapid advancement and growth in the field of technology, with all other benefits it has also aided the study of complementation patterns with the help of corpus. Corpus is a rapid growing field and approach in the field of linguistics to study language especially for not native speakers. It is quite helpful and beneficial for not native language users when it comes to opt for any specific complementation pattern for a verb.

Language is not static but a dynamic phenomenon, it undergoes constant process evolution and change. It can also grow with relation to words and expressions as different communities use it they create and adopt new entities for it create divergence. Languages also die bit by bit as the lexical items become obsolete, their speakers just adopt any other language and do away with their language.

One of the big reasons is colonization as the British colonizer took the language to the different colonies. English intermixed with the local languages and in result of which differences appear. Differences in lexical items are important to describe the variations in the language, it is known as the descriptive way of studying the language. The other approach to study language is diachronic way to study language. Bolinger (1981) stated that variation is not noticeable on the scale of human life time so grammar can be an important and interesting parameter to study language change.

This particular study aims to work on the aspect of verb complementation patterns in the Pakistani English from diachronic perspective. Verb complementation pattern in Pakistani English has been studied been studied in the past by Hassan & Mahmood (2014) but the attempt to study complementation aspect of Pakistani English diachronically is the first attempt.

Hassan & Mahmood (2014) studied the verb complementation patterns by using Pakistani Written English (PWE). The PWE is a corpus of written Pakistani English having 29 different written text categories, 1,477 files, and 2,119,626 words. In this study 1867 sentences were analyzed manually. Frequency and distribution of verb complementation patterns were calculated and research conclude that there is the influence of local languages and culture on English language. In result of which differences in complementation patterns appear.

Sassure (1916) devised the terms synchronic (static, specific time) and diachronic (different times) to study languages and language variations. Diachronic studies include language variation with the passage of time and comparison of linguistic behaviors across different time spans.

Researcher intends to study the diachronic variation of verb complementation pattern of Pakistani English. Two kinds of patterns gerundive and to infinitive patterns are found. Researcher intends to study the change in the frequency and trend of gerundive and to infinitive patterns.

Diachronic corpus of Pakistani written English is collected for the research. Corpus consisted upon books, articles, journals, legal language such as acts and proceedings. Researcher took data of four decades from 1947 to 1986. Researcher analyzed the data in the form of four decades ranging from 1947 to 1956, 1957 to 1966, 1967 to 1976, and 1977 to 1986 to identify and check the variations of verb complementation pattern diachronically.

2.0 Review of Literature

Tense, mode and aspect are studied quite frequently in syntax variations during the last decade. Among tense, aspect and modality complementation has also been given equal importance to determine the semantics of verb. Complementation of verb completes the specifications of the meanings which verbs carries (Quirk, 1985). Verb complementation is a structural feature of language and is considered more significant in giving a variety its character lexical items. It has significant theoretical interest in both the generative tradition (Saleemi, 1993) and in construction grammar (Croft, 1998).

Some later researches studied the Kolhapur corpus, a one-million-word corpus designed to be parallel to the American Brown and British LOB corpora. Leitner (1994), for example, gives an analysis of the complementation of begin and start in these three collections. As we would expect, he observed no vivid differences between 'native' Brown and LOB vis-à-vis 'non-native' Kolhapur, but there were few variations among these three varieties.

Biber (1999) differentiate four major structural types of complement clauses, and these are; that-clauses, wh-clauses, to-infinitive clauses, and ing-clauses. All these types of complements are used for the different purposes and they may carry different kinds of discourse functions, i.e, thatclause is used mainly to report the speech (Biber, 1999). That-clauses and to-infinitive clauses are found twice than the wh-clauses and ing-clauses (Biber et al., 1999). Biber (1999) also pointed out that there is choice to keep 'that' as complementizer or to omit it.

To explain the main differences between complements and adjuncts, Huddleston & Pullum (2002) use the following example:

He | always | reads | the paper | before breakfast.

C A P C A

The paper is the complement of the verb reads and it is tightly bound with the verb, it is possessing the syntactic characteristics. Huddleston & Pullum (2002) point out that adjunct is loosely bound to clause as compared to complement and adjunct performs semantic roles in the sentences. Sentence cannot be considered complete without complement but can stand without adjuncts.

Huddleston & Pullum (2002) differentiate altogether eight factors which help to differentiate between complements and adjuncts. These factors are called licensing, obligatoriness, anaphora, category, position, argument-hood, selection and role. The first five factors are related to syntactic differences, and the rest have to deal with semantic issues.

This study aims to study the patterns. Hunston (2002) explains the reason why patterns are significant and the importance to study the patterns. She describes 'pattern' as "an arrangement of grammatical units, word types or clause types which are found in neighborhood of a given lexical item. An item may be stated to possess control or 'have' a pattern if that pattern is found frequently and is dependent on the item which is in question" (Hunston, 2002).

2.1 Hypothesis

Bomgardner (1993) claimed about the Pakistani English that Pakistani users of English language prefer to use (to infinitive) pattern as compared to gerundive.

To infinitive> He likes to play cricket.

Gerundive>He likes playing cricket.

Keeping this view as starting point researcher tried to find out whether this statement about Pakistani English is true or not. Researcher tried study this aspect by finding out those verbs which carry both these patterns as verb complementation.

Aziz (2010) conducted the study on verb complementation pattern and enlisted those verbs which carry to infinitive pattern as compliment of the verb. Those verbs are enlisted in the table below.

Table 2.1

Advice	Allow	Ask	Cause	Command
Permit	Persuade	Pressure	Prompt	Instruct
Compel	Direct	Encourage	Expect	Want
Forbid	Force	Order	Inspire	Warn
Recommend	Require	Teach	Tell	Urge

The above mentioned table contains verbs which carry to infinitive pattern. Researcher intended to compare the frequency and gradual development and change in the usage of (to infinitive) and gerundive pattern.

The other idea which researcher tried to find out was to find out the gradual development of this tendency to prefer (to infinitive) as compared to gerundive complementation pattern. English language was brought to Pakistan by British speakers. After getting independence from British rulers in 1947 Pakistan became independent and began to make constitutions and other legal activities to make the country stabilized.

National newspaper is in the service since the emergence of country. Since the emergence of Pakistan, Pakistani writers began to write with the influence of local language and with different features.

Researcher hypothesized that the tendency to write with the (to infinitive) complement increased with the passage of time. Researcher intends to investigate the chronological progression of the tendency to prefer (to infinitive) over gerundive complement.

1. The habit of preferring (to infinitive) complement over gerundive complement with the passage of time.

2.2 Research Questions

1. What is the frequency of complementation pattern of the verbs containing gerundive and infinitive common as complementation?

2. What are the different diachronic variations in the frequency of the complementation patterns? 3. What is the ratio of gerundive and infinitive patterns with the portions of ICE corpora of other varieties?

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Corpus collection

1st step in this research was to collect the diachronic corpus. For that purpose, corpus from books, articles, journals, newspaper and legal language was collected diachronically. Most of the text was available in hard form such as books, newspapers and legal text. Corpus was collected year wise and all texts were kept separately. The next step was to combine all texts and genres in one file of the particular year to make a combined file of that particular year. The next step was to combine the files decade wise to make a justifiable distribution and make the corpus ready for further analysis.

3.2 Verbs Selection

Researcher intended to study the complementation pattern of verbs in Pakistani English. Aziz (2010) reported verbs in Pakistani English which carry (to infinitive) pattern.

Table 3.1

Advice	Allow	Ask	Cause	Command	Compel
Direct	Encourage	Expect	Forbid	Force	Inspire
Instruct	Order	Permit	Persuade	Pressure	Prompt
Recommend	Require	Teach	Tell	Urge	Want
want	Warn				

For the purpose of conducting the comparative study of gerundive and (to infinitive) pattern researcher needed those verbs which carry gerundive as complementation pattern. For that purpose researcher used the online sources of books4language, grammar quiz and English to collect the verbs which carry gerundive pattern.

Table 3.2

Admit	Advice	Avoid	Deny	Dislike	Forget
Love	Neglect	Prevent	Regret	Risk	Support
Tolerate	Support	Start	Remember	Postpone	Prohibit
Mention	Try	Understand	Stop	Suggest	Resist
Resent	Quit	Recall	Practice	Prefer	Mind
Miss Hate	Imagine	Enjoy	Keep	Finish	Escape
Deserve	Discuss	Consider	Celebrate	Complete	Recommend
Like	Allow	Anticipate	Appreciate	Delay	

The next step was to find out those common verbs which carry both complementation pattern without the change in meaning. Those verbs were selected which were present in the both categories.

Table 3.3

Attempt	Allow	Begin	Continue	Deserve
Enjoy	Forget	Hate	Intend	Like
Love	Need	Prefer	Recommend	Require
Remember	Regret	Stop	Start	Try

3.3 Corpus Analysis

2nd Step was to analyze the corpus. Corpus was analyzed with the help of Antconc. The Antconc is the utility software which helps to analyze the corpus. Concordance lines of those twenty verbs which contain both gerundive and to infinitive complementation pattern were developed. Verbs such as allow, attempt, begin, continue, deserve, enjoy, forget, hate, intend, like, love, need, prefer, recommend, regret, remember, require, start, stop and try were the verbs were studied.

At the next phase of the study a piloting was done to make sure that all these verbs and their patterns exist in one of the corpora. All verbs were studied and the occurrence of both patterns was found in the corpus. The next step was to study each verb one by one and study the patterns of the verbs.

After developing the concordance line of these verbs with lemma form and all forms of the verbs, concordance lines were taken to the excel sheet and the frequency of the both patterns were analyzed and counted. Concordance line of each verb was studied one by one and after the analysis of the three forms of all these twenty verbs frequency of these patterns were extracted and reported in the result section.

Frequency of the occurrence of patterns of all twenty verbs was studied and analyzed in all four corpora. Frequency of the complementation pattern was studied in each corpus separately to find out the gradual variation and change in the tendency of patterns. All four corpora were of different size and the size of corpus may effect on the frequency of the patterns. To neutralize the affect frequency of patterns was normalized.

Formula which was used for the purpose of normalizing was to divide the frequency of occurrence of patterns over the total tokens of the corpus and multiply with 100,000. Frequency of patterns/total tokens of corpus x 100,000= normalized frequency.

4.1 Results and Discussion

Frequency of complementation pattern in 1947 to 1986

Table 4.1

Verbs	1947-56		1957-66		1967-76		1977-86	
	To Infinitive	Gerund						
Allow	136	4	289	3	555	6	641	6
Attempt	217	7	511	38	650	47	1070	6
Begin	87	28	497	70	773	92	1085	101
Continue	167	16	352	39	609	78	1049	103
Deserve	11	4	3	2	4	2	13	1
Enjoy	0	1	0	6	0	5	0	7
Forget	0	2	12	0	10	0	22	2
Hate	1	0	0	1	1	1	11	1
Intend	89	5	158	2	251	8	524	11
Like	188	8	299	19	581	53	671	55
Love	0	0	6	2	21	0	32	4
Need	17	1	167	17	167	23	431	69
Prefer	24	6	43	6	87	8	147	11
Recommend	0	0	0	0	4	2	13	2
Regret	8	2	11	3	15	4	18	4
Remember	1	0	262	12	0	1	0	11
Require	81	8	4	1	301	26	508	16
Start	9	95	35	247	51	376	92	655
Stop	3	5	6	56	6	80	10	71
Try	170	1	473	2	889	3	966	3

Above mentioned table showed the frequency of both patterns occurring in all four corpora. Most of the times frequency of (to infinitive) pattern is much frequent and has been found in very much higher frequency as compared to the gerundive compliment. Gerund has also been found as the compliment pattern of verbs but (to infinitive) pattern is much more frequent as compared to (to infinitive) pattern.

Slight differences were observed in the occurrence of both complementation patterns. Frequency of gerundive pattern is more than (to infinitive) pattern with few words. Frequency of the pattern of the verb remember is quite interesting it shows variations and few frequent occurrences of gerundive compliment than the (to infinitive) constructions.

Start is the verb found in all corpora which take gerundive compliment on a much higher frequency as compared to (to infinitive) pattern. Results in all corpora showed the higher frequency of gerundive compliment over (to infinitive). It can be the impact of collocation pattern of the verb start which possesses gerundive at a higher frequency.

Another kind of compliment pattern (to+1st form+ing) is also found as compliment pattern in other varieties of English but Pakistani writers do not choose this construction as compliment pattern. Only three occurrences were found of such pattern in all corpora. Pakistani writers while preferring (to infinitive) pattern avoid the more complex pattern and keep their writings simple.

The above mentioned tables showed the frequencies of the complementation patterns of the verbs of all forms but these frequencies were raw frequencies and need to be normalized because of the variation in the size of the corpus variation in the frequency of occurrences of patterns is an obvious thing and it needs to be normalized.

For that purpose, frequency of the occurrences of the patterns were divided over the total tokens of the corpora.

Table 4.2

Corpus	Tokens
1947 to 1956	1791289
1957 to 1966	2120802
1967 to 1976	2270886
1977 to 1986	2939433

The results extracted after normalizing the frequencies of the patterns are more justified and the results can elaborate the study more efficiently. Normalized results show the differences in the frequency of the patterns.

The first decade showed the results of the patterns in the corpus from 1947 to 1956. Most of the verbs carry (to infinitive) pattern as more frequently than the gerundive pattern. But keeping in mind the fact that the corpus of 1947 comprised upon the corpus consisting upon the data of the early era of the beginning of the Pakistan and Pakistani variety with the influence of local languages affecting the usage of English language.

Early era of Pakistan and the usage of the English by Pakistani writers was influenced by British who brought the English to Pakistan. British had the influence on Pakistani users and it appeared in the frequency of the patterns of the corpus of the 1st decade. Verbs such as enjoy, start and stop have the gerundive pattern as more frequent pattern than the (to infinitive) pattern. It shows the influence of British (mother) variety on Pakistani English but this influence gradually changed.

Verbs such as love and recommend did not show any occurrence in the corpus with the complementation pattern with (to infinitive) or gerundive.

The second decade showed the results of the patterns in the corpus of the 2nd decade after the emergence of Pakistani variety. The trend, tendency and the preferences of the writers shifted and Pakistani writers began to show the independent behavior and use (to infinitive) pattern more frequently as compared to gerundive as verb complementation pattern. Verbs such as enjoy, start and stop carried gerundive as complementation pattern more frequently as compared to (to infinitive) pattern. The verb 'recommend' did not show any occurrence with the (to infinitive) or gerundive as verb complementation pattern.

Tendency of the patterns continued shifting and changing from the beginning and the same appeared in the results of the third decade. Verbs such as remember, stop and enjoy showed the higher frequency of gerundive as verb complementation pattern. Verb 'start' showed different results in this decade of results. Start in this decade possessed (to infinitive) more frequently as compared to gerundive pattern.

In the 4th decade corpus the verbs such as enjoy, start and stop carried gerundive pattern more frequently than the (to infinitive) pattern. Results carried the occurrence of all verbs with both complementation patterns.

Table Of Frequency Of Verbs In All Decades Table

Table 4.3

Verbs	1947-56		1957-66		1967-76		1977-86	
	To Infinitive	Gerund						
Allow	7.59	0.22	13.63	0.14	24.44	0.26	21.81	0.20
Attempt	12.11	0.39	24.09	1.79	28.62	2.07	36.40	0.20
Begin	4.86	1.56	23.43	3.30	34.04	4.05	36.91	3.44
Continue	3.74	0.89	16.60	1.84	26.82	3.43	35.69	3.50
Deserve	0.61	0.22	0.14	0.09	0.18	0.09	0.44	0.03
Enjoy	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.28	0.00	0.22	0.00	0.24
Forget	0.00	0.11	0.57	0.00	0.44	0.00	0.75	0.07
Hate	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.37	0.03
Intend	4.97	0.28	7.45	0.09	11.05	0.35	17.83	0.37
Like	10.50	0.45	14.10	0.90	25.58	2.33	22.83	1.87
Love	0.00	0.00	0.28	0.09	0.92	0.00	1.09	0.14
Need	0.95	0.06	7.87	0.80	7.35	1.01	14.66	2.35
Prefer	1.34	0.33	2.03	0.28	3.83	0.35	5.00	0.37
Recommend	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.18	0.09	0.44	0.07
Regret	0.45	0.11	0.52	0.14	0.66	0.18	0.61	0.14
Remember	0.06	0.00	0.19	0.05	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.37
Require	4.52	0.45	12.35	0.57	13.25	1.14	17.28	0.54
Start	0.50	5.30	1.65	11.65	22.50	16.56	3.13	22.28
Stop	0.17	0.28	0.28	2.64	0.26	3.52	0.34	2.42
Try	9.49	0.06	22.30	0.09	39.15	0.13	32.86	0.10

The table above shows the overall tendency, frequency and shift of patterns. Among these twenty verbs, the verbs such as enjoy and stop throughout the history showed the higher frequency of gerundive construction than the (to infinitive) construction. The verb start possessed gerundive more

frequent in three decades but not in the 3rd decade of results. Verbs such as love, enjoy, forget, hate and recommend did not show any occurrence in the beginning but later on kept on containing both complementation pattern.

Results show the proper evolution, tendency of shift and linguistic change throughout the history. Diachronic variations are observed in the results. Results of the verb 'allow' show gradual evolution in all four corpora and the frequency of occurrence of the (to infinitive) pattern is observed as increasing diachronically.

Few verbs showed the tendency of increasing both complement patterns (to infinitive and gerundive) gradually. Results of the verb 'continue' showed the gradual progression of the increase of both patterns. To infinitive pattern has more frequent occurrences than the gerundive patterns with the verb 'continue' in all decades.

Collective Frequency of To infinitive and Gerundive

Table 4.4

	To Infinitive	Gerundive
1947 to 1956	61.91	10.77
1957 to 1956	147.49	24.80
1967 to 1976	239.33	35.89
1977 to 1986	248.45	38.75
Total	691.18	110.21

Collective results of the occurrences of (to infinitive) and gerundive patterns shows increase in the tendency of the usage of both patterns. Frequency of both continued to increase with the passage of time. Results show the major difference in the occurrence of gerundive and to infinitive pattern. To infinitive pattern much more frequent than the gerundive pattern.

4.2 Comparison with Native varieties

Deshors and Gries (2016) conducted the comparative study of gerundive and to infinitive patterns among native and non-native varieties of English. For that purpose, British and American represented native varieties and Hong-Kong, Indian and Singaporean varieties represented nonnative varieties. International corpus of English (ICE) was used for the study and analyzed complementation pattern among these Asian non-native varieties. Research concluded that Asian varieties are more close to American English than the British English.

Table 4.5

Complementation pattern	ICE_GB	ICE_US	ICE_HK	ICE_IND	ICE_SING
To-infinitive	990	781	753	531	753
Gerundive	84	187	126	102	128
Total	1074	968	879	633	881

The above table shows the comparative frequency of gerundive and to infinitive pattern among native and non-native varieties of English. At the end results of the Pakistani variety are compared with the British variety. Pakistani variety showed the ratio of 346:55 and British variety showed the result of 156:14. Frequency of (To infinitive) are reported at higher ratio than gerund.

Nominalization

Long man dictionary defined the term 'gerund' as words which works as noun in the form of the present participle of the verb. The word in the example 'I like eating' is gerund and works as compliment of the verb. Same meaning can be conveyed by constructing the sentence 'I like to eat'. In this preceding example to infinitive pattern is found as complement.

Both options are available to the writer to infinitive and gerund as compliment. Writer can go for any option to write and convey the message. Gerund works as noun in the sentence. Sentence on English has a basis structure of SVO.

Subject	Verb	Object
Noun	Verb	Noun
Smoking is injurious to health.		
Ali does not like smoking.		

Gerund works as noun and be placed at the place of either subject or object. Compliment of the verb comes adjacent to verb and work as complement. Verb can go for either to infinitive complement or gerundive complement.

Non-native speakers and writers like Pakistani speakers prefer to use to infinitive as compared to gerund. Gerund works as noun and make the writing more complex for the writer to construct and for reader to read and deconstruct and extract the meaning. Pakistani writers have the higher tendency to write with to infinitive as compared to gerund.

Non-native speakers do not have that much greater grip and competence like native speakers. Though kachru (1988) states that native non-native distinction should be abolished. That claim comes with the perspective of authority. Three circle model by kachru (1985) Inner circle, outer circle and expanding circle distinguish three basic categories of language users.

Inner circle includes ENL speakers for whom English is native language. Outer circle includes ESL speakers; English is second language for them. Expanding circle includes EFL category of speakers; English is foreign language for them. ENL includes countries like USA, UK and Australia. ESL includes India, Pakistan, Hong Kong and Singapore. EFL includes countries like China and Russia. ENL countries are norm provider. ESL countries are norm developer and ESL countries are norm Follower.

Speakers of Pakistan are partially norm follower and partially norm developer. These speakers inherit few norms from native speakers and follow those norms and they have little contribution and develop their norms which arouse on the basis of mother tongue. They develop their own way of pronunciation influenced by their mother tongue. They have their own stock of lexical items and they have their own syntactic pattern influenced by their mother tongue.

Non-native speakers have different and distinct features of language usage. Distinct usage of lexical items, different pronunciations, different semantic features and grammatical elements make the difference. The more frequent usage of (to infinitive) then gerund make the Pakistani variety distinctive from others and make it a distinctive feature of Pakistani English.

5.0 Conclusion

It can be concluded from the study that Pakistani speakers use to infinitive at a much greater frequency than the gerund as verb complement. Results taken from the study revealed that the statement of bomgardner (1993) taken as the hypothesis was correct. Results showed the higher

frequency of (to infinitive) then (gerund) as verb complement. A proper change and shift was observed in the tendency to use (infinitive) as compared to (gerund). Data was taken in the form of four decades from 1947 to 1986. Results of the corpora of all decades showed over all higher frequency of (to infinitive). Further these results make a distinctive feature of Pakistani English. Pakistani speakers being non-native speakers of English language prefer to use (to infinitive) pattern over gerund as verb complement. Gerund works as noun in the sentence. Process of nominalization makes the writing more complex. Pakistani non-native speakers do not opt for gerundive pattern at a higher frequency to keep their writing simple and easy to comprehend.

5.1 Further studies

Research leads to further options of research. This study was conducted on data from 1947 to 1986. Research recommends to conduct a parallel study on two corpora a native and non-native which would elaborate the idea clearly about the usage of these patterns and chronological shift about the tendency to use these patterns. Equal size and proportion of the data in a diachronic order should be taken as parallel corpora to conduct a more vivid study about the usage of patterns and change in the trend.

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